

Dialectics of Traditional Authority and Post-Colonial Modern State: The Case of Somaliland

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Abstract:

This article investigates the development of states within societies that have undergone colonization, with a specific focus on Somaliland and its clan-based structure. Our aim is to contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding the interplay between traditional clan affiliations and the pursuit of a nation-state, which is a critical issue with significant implications for political stability and international recognition in the region. To achieve this, we employ a methodology that includes reviewing relevant literature, synthesizing theoretical perspectives, and conducting in-depth sociological

analyses, incorporating Weberian ideas of authority into our examination. This comprehensive approach enables us to gain a deeper understanding of Somaliland's unique socio-political landscape, which has been shaped by its colonial past and entrenched tribal dynamics. In our analysis, we critically assess the role of clan structures, such as the Guurti council, and their relationship with attempts to establish a rational state system. Our findings indicate that although clannism remains deeply ingrained in Somaliland's society, achieving harmony between these affiliations and modern state-building initiatives is crucial for the region's progress. In conclusion, we synthesize these insights to provide recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of strategies that recognize and address the dynamics of clan affiliations while promoting a strong state identity. Adopting such an approach is essential for fostering stability in Somaliland and supporting its aspirations for recognition.

Keywords: *Somaliland, Somalia, Statehood, Traditional Authority*

Introduction: Unraveling Somaliland's Socio-Political Tapestry

This article explores the unique case of Somaliland, a self-declared republic in the Horn of Africa with a complex interplay between traditional clannism and modern statehood aspirations. The study delves into the socio-political landscape of Somaliland, highlighting the resilience of its people and their struggle for international recognition. The story of Somaliland is not only a regional concern but also resonates with broader themes of post-

colonial state formation, identity politics, and democratization in tribal societies. This article examines the historical, cultural, and political factors that have shaped Somaliland's journey from British colonial rule to its declaration of independence from Somalia in 1991, and its ongoing quest for international recognition.

Central to Somaliland's socio-political landscape is the concept of clannism, an entrenched social structure that has defined Somali society for centuries. In Somaliland, the influence of clans extends beyond social organization and is deeply

ingrained in the political fabric. This article explores how clannism, while providing social order and solidarity, poses significant challenges to the establishment of a modern democratic state. The tension between clan allegiances and statehood building lies at the heart of Somaliland's ongoing dilemma.

Somaliland's navigation of socio-political challenges offers valuable insights into the possibilities and perils of nation-building in a clan-based society. The region's efforts in peacebuilding, state formation, and democratization amidst the stronghold of tribal affiliations provide a unique lens through which to explore the dynamics at play in Somaliland. This article seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of these dynamics and to provide a nuanced perspective that goes beyond the typical narratives of conflict and instability in the Horn of Africa, highlighting the region's efforts towards carving a unique path in the modern geopolitical landscape.

In the following sections, we will examine the historical context of Somaliland's formation, the interplay between clannism and the state-building process, and the implications of these dynamics for Somaliland's future and its quest for international recognition.

Methodology

The methodology utilized in this article employs a multifaceted approach that integrates an analytical literature review, theoretical synthesis, and sociological analysis, all while focusing on the intricate relationship between traditional authority, clannism, and statehood in Somaliland. By incorporating Weber's sociological theories of authority and conducting a comprehensive examination of the literature on Somaliland's socio-political dynamics, tribalism, and state-building, the study extends its analysis to encompass a broader spectrum of perspectives. This approach enables a nuanced synthesis of empirical case studies with broader theoretical frameworks, with a specific emphasis on the dynamics of traditional and legal-rational authority. The methodology adheres to ethical

principles, academic integrity, and objectivity, with the ultimate aim of contributing to a deeper, sociologically informed understanding of clannism and authority in Somaliland's statehood discourse.

Authority in Transition: Sociological Perspectives on Traditional and Modern Governance

Max Weber's analysis of authority is crucial for understanding political legitimacy and governance. Weber (1947) identified three pure types of authority: traditional, charismatic, and legal-rational. In Somaliland, the interplay between traditional and legal-rational authority is particularly pronounced. Traditional authority, according to Weber, is established by long-standing customs and inherited positions (Weber, 1947). This type of authority is prevalent in societies where historical and cultural practices are deeply embedded, such as in the clan-based structure of Somaliland.

Somaliland presents a classic example of traditional authority in practice. The clan system, integral to Somaliland's social fabric, exemplifies Weber's traditional authority, where respect and compliance are rooted in age-old customs (Lewis, 1961). Bradbury (2008) further illustrates how these traditional structures provide not just social order but also a sense of identity and belonging. However, as Drysdale, (1964) argues, the reliance on clan loyalty and traditional norms can pose significant challenges to the centralization and modernization efforts in state-building processes.

The aspiration for a modern state in post-colonial contexts often involves a shift towards Weber's concept of legal-rational authority. This form of authority relies on legal, institutionalized procedures and is the hallmark of modern state governance (Weber, 1947). In Somaliland, the drive towards building democratic institutions and implementing legal reforms reflects this transition. (Walls, 2009) notes that these efforts represent a significant move away from clan-based governance towards a more structured, rule-based state system.

The case of Somaliland reveals a complex dialectic between traditional and modern forms of authority. Eisenstadt, (1973) argues that such transitions are not linear but involve continuous negotiation and adaptation between different forms of authority. Laakso & Hautaniemi, (2014) specifically examines how in Somaliland, this negotiation process is evident in the coexistence of and sometimes tensions between clan loyalties and the developing state institutions. This dynamic interplay highlights the challenges and opportunities in navigating the path from traditional to modern statehood.

Understanding the dialectic between traditional and legal-rational authority has significant implications for nation-building, especially in post-colonial contexts. Kaplan (2008) emphasizes that policies aimed at state-building must consider the intricate balance between these forms of authority. Jhazbhay (2009) uses Somaliland as a case study to demonstrate how traditional structures can be effectively integrated into the modern state apparatus, thereby creating a more inclusive and stable governance model. The Weberian concept of authority provides a valuable framework for analyzing the state-building process in Somaliland. The interplay between traditional and legal-rational authority in Somaliland serves as a vital case study for understanding the complexities involved in transitioning from a clan-based society to a modern state.

Historical Tapestry: The Genesis of Somaliland's Statehood

Before the arrival of the colonial, Somalis were organized into different clans dispersed in the Somali lands. Colonials divided Somalis into five the British protectorate (currently Somaliland), Somalia (South Somalia), Djibouti, Ogaden (now the Somali Region in Ethiopia), and Northern Frontier District (NFD). Somaliland was announced as a British Protectorate (Bradbury, 2008; Farley, 2010; Spears, 2010). After decades under the British colony, the British Protectorate acquired its independence on June 26, 1960 (Bradbury, 2008; Farley, 2010; Jhazbhay, 2009; Samatar, 2002). After five days of its

independence, Somaliland united with the Italian colonized Southern Somalia and to form the Somali Republic on July 1, 1960, and seek the missing other three Somali regions to create the greater Somali state (Bradbury, 2008; Farley, 2010; Jhazbhay, 2009; Lewis, 2003; Samatar, 2002).

British Somalilanders were exceptionally compelling for the union's consummation, though the Italian Somalilanders favored proceeding cautiously. Italian Somaliland's legislators favored the union's postponement to solve the undecided issues. However, British Somalilanders supposed the union's deferment might desire to be a weakness and thrust to speed up it."I noted with alarm that the people of Somaliland had forced the union upon the South so precipitously that they alone had to pay the price by accepting a southern constitution, southern flag, the southern capital, and a southern Head of State – who also appointed a southern Prime Minister," noted Jama Mohamed Ghalib (as cited in Spears, 2010, p. 129). After taking the president, Italian Somalilanders also took heavyweight ministries. British Somaliland took only 33 seats of the 123 National Assembly (SCPD (Somaliland Center for Peace and Development), 1999; Spears, 2010). This inequality in power-sharing ultimately triggered British Somaliland's grievance, feelings of loss, and disillusionment among Somalis (Bradbury, 2008)

Presumably, it was soon for Somalilanders to realize that they made a mistake in uniting with Somalia without legal guidance (Hansen & Bradbury, 2007, p. 463; Pham, 2010, p. 140). It seemed increasingly clear that the leaders of Southern Somalia would dominate them in government power-sharing. Democratic principles guided the political arrangements and constitution after independence. According to literature, 1960 and 1969 was the golden age of democracy in Somalia's history (Bradbury, 2008; Elmi, 2010; Hansen & Bradbury, 2007; Ismail, 2010; Samatar, 2002)." After two administrations, power-sharing was democratically divided into the Southern or Somalia took a president, while the northern or Somaliland was left with a prime-ministership"

(Samatar, 2008). This issue brings the appearance of equity between Somaliland and Somalia.

However, the actuality was different, and it created a stir among the people of Somaliland as a result of the government's marginalization and alienation with northerners. Besides, the democratic system was increasing, failing, and corruption became rampant. Divided tribal politics and rampant corruption permeated the government (SCPD., p. 15). Both the evils of political tribalism and widespread corruption perpetrated by tribal men who wanted to run for the 1967 elections have led to instability, disrepute for Somalis, undermined state-building, and hastened the assassination of the president. Abdirashid Ali Sharmarke. Both the evils of political tribalism and widespread corruption perpetrated by tribal men who wanted to run for the 1967 (Bradbury, 2008; Farley, 2010; Hansen & Bradbury, 2007) elections have led to instability, disrepute for Somalis, undermined state-building, and hastened president Abdirashid Ali Sharmarke's assassination on October 15 1969.

Tribal politics and widespread corruption have led to unrest in the country, with the military seizing power in a bloodless coup on October 21, 1969, much to the delight of the coup leaders (Elmi, 2010; Ismail, 2010; Kusow, 2004; Lewis, 2003; Samatar, 2008; Spears, 2010). The Supreme Revolutionary Council (SRC) has issued a statement saying it has taken over control of the country from the parties. The SRC fought against tribalism, clan politics, nepotism, and ordinary people widely welcomed SRC's steps. The military government stated that tribalism is cancer in society. They made it clear that it was necessary to eradicate and move towards a modern state-building process. In foreign policy, the military regime opted the Soviet Union its close ally. The Soviets, as compensation, provided economic and military to Somalia estimated at \$50 million in 1972 (Khapoya & Agyeman-Duah, 1985). The military government was grateful for "huge work projects, modernization efforts, and attempts to unify the Somali administration's two components" (Farley, 2010). The regimes' most

significant triumph belongs to the education sector; it wrote the Somali language into Latin script (Ismail, 2010).

Nevertheless, the military regime remained repressive, tight, and brutal (Bade, 2020; Farley, 2010) due to the administration's alienation from most other clans. Bereketeab (2012) noted that "Pervasive political repression by the regime and the accompanying economic and security deterioration provoked widespread dissatisfaction and rebellion, thereby undermining the project of state-building" (Bereketeab, 2012). The most astonishing collective narrative is that the military government's breakdown commenced with the war's consequences against Ethiopia in 1977 (SCPD (Somaliland Center for Peace and Development), 1999). Somalia's loss of war with Ethiopia hastened the Somali state's fall (Mengisteab, 2011, p. 11; Walls & Kibble, 2010, p. 38). The first signal of breakage within the military government power system arrived following the failed coup lead by Abdillahi Yusuf, and his clan members tried to overthrow the military government after the Ethio-Somali catastrophe in 1978. The Majeerteen clan was the main plotters of the failed coup against the military government in 1978. Afterward, in retaliation, the regime committed atrocities in Mudug and Bari regions, Majerteen's key settlements. In reaction, the Somali Salvation Democratic Front (SSDF), a clan-based movement, was formed against the military regime (Bade, 2020; Farley, 2010; Møller, 2009).

Moreover, the military government's extreme atrocities and authoritarianism paved the way for the other clan-based movement in the 1980s. Somali National Movement (SNM), one of Ethiopia's most significant, was founded in 1981 (Bade, 2020; Mengisteab, 2011; Møller, 2009). The Somali civil-war became fierce during the 1980s. Bereketeab 2012, noted that "In a desperate measure to stay in power and suppress the rebellion, the regime's army bombed towns indiscriminately" (Bereketeab, 2012). Hargeisa, the capital city of current Somaliland, was of such a profoundly bombed town with destruction. The war's act not merely backed SNM's claim to depose the military regime but

also to reconsider with the union and, more importantly, Somaliland's self-determination. "The immense suffering the Issaq clan were subjected to by the Siad Barre regime during the war, and the domination of the Somali state by southerners finally convinced the Issaq clan to opt for secession, with the idea of independence coming later" (Bereketeab, 2012). The gigantic sorrow and impact of the military government's actions during the war, besides Southern's state domination, was the vital narrative that convinced SNM to choose for separation idea of independence in 1991. Finally, the result of fierce civil war led to the military regime's fall in 1991.

The country's rule went into militant's hands. The United Somali Congress (USC) took Mogadishu, the Somali capital, whereas the SNM controlled Hargeisa, the second biggest city, declared its independence from Somalian on May 18, 1991. Somaliland's secession was because Somaliland was a separate state created by the British colonialists and then united with southern Somalia; when they did not understand each other, they had the right to self-determination. Two issues caused the acceleration of Somaliland's independence declaration. Those formed a unilateral government in Mogadishu without consultation with the SNM and pressure within Somaliland's population (Bade, 2020; Bryden, 2004). Bereketeab mentions, "the first two years following the unilateral declaration of independence were fraught with conflict and war" (Bereketeab, 2012). The clans that were not supportive of SNM instead backed the military regime involved conflict with Issaq subjugated SNM. After taking over, SNM reconsidered to reconcile the opposing groups through negotiations intended abolition of hostility to avoid devastating vengeance acts. The Borama national reconciliation conference established Somaliland's bedrock of state formation. "The non-Issaq clans, albeit reluctantly, seemed to have accepted the idea of Somaliland statehood" (Bereketeab, 2012).

The leading figures of SNM proposed clan elders for mediation between disputing groups. Accordingly, the Somaliland clans Issaq,

Gadabursi, Harti (Dhulbahante and Warsangeli), Issa, and other clans prepared and sent their representatives to Borama's conference on national elder's council (guurti), produced transition of power to the civilian government (Walls & Kibble, 2010, p. 40). The elder's council (guurti) elected former Somali prime minister Mohamed Haji Ibrahim Egal, and Somaliland entered a democratic and civilian rule system, and SNM abandoned the power.

Thus, to build public confidence and develop the government, President Egal announced a multi-party system. Ambitious parties have been called upon to come up with an inclusive platform. They were also warned against clan and religious group affiliations. Succeeding Somaliland's referendum in 2001, Somaliland also implemented its constitution based on a parliament's bicameral system. The guurti (elders) were allocated for the upper house and elected assembly for the lower house. After president Egal's death, Somaliland elected Dahir Riyale Kahin as succeeding president in 2003. In 2005, Rayale successfully implemented parliamentary elections.

In utilizing the democratization and electoral process, Ahmed Mohamed Mahamoud "Silaanyo" won over Riyale's ruling part in June 2010. Again, in 2012, Somaliland successfully and peacefully conducted local government council elections. More importantly, in 2017, Somaliland went into the presidential election in which the current president, Muse Bihi Abdi, Somaliland's 5th president, came to power. Thus, free elections and the transfer of power in succession improved to the state-building in Somaliland.

Somaliland expected that its successful democratization process would increase a chance of attaining international recognition. Receiving some understanding and appreciation from some countries, including the United Kingdom, South Africa, Ethiopia, Kenya, and Rwanda, no single country has recognized Somaliland today. Bryden argues that "for Somalilanders, the declaration of independence was not an act of secession, but was, rather, the reclaiming of a sovereignty they voluntarily gave

up" (Bryden, 2004). Factually, Somaliland remains secure and stable where power was peacefully transferred in every election (Bradbury, 2008; Pham, 2010). "This is attributed to the successful conflation of traditional clan structures and a modern representative polity, but also to 'avoiding revenge and achieving a successful reconciliation'" (Bereketeab, 2012). These developments led Somaliland to arise as a political entity from a conflict-ridden context, complicated and highly destructive, putting Somaliland statehood negotiation's stage.

In this regard, clan structures contributed and played a constructive role in Somaliland's peacebuilding. Bereketeab said, "clan mechanisms and institutions of conflict resolution have been decisive in, at least, mitigating conflicts and managing disputes and thus in bringing relative peace and stability" (Bereketeab, 2012). Certainly, Somaliland experienced a fruitful way to state-building. However, the border dispute with Somalia's Federal Government Member, Puntland, may hinder Somaliland's international recognition mission. Additionally, Somaliland challenged an international pressure to join the Somali reconstitution process and participated at the London conference in 2012. Since 2012, Somaliland negotiated with Somalia over self-determination, but there are no fruitful outcomes from those negotiations.

Crafting a Nation: The Evolution of Somaliland's Political Landscape

The state of nature welcomed the return of Somaliland as an independent state to its previous agreement in the Republic of Somalia. Hamilton (2013), describes the state of nature as "a war of all against all, in which people are constantly trying to destroy each other for the pursuit of power". Life is nasty, short, and brutish in the state of nature. In this respect, Barre seized control and exerted it over other individuals to marginalize them for his clan's gain. The Republic's natural law made citizens unequal, and the associates of Barre kept the executive power of natural law and used it to

exclude others. Barre committed perpetual massacres during his reign of terror. Summary executions, arbitrary arrests, targeted assassinations, evictions, freezing commercial operations, and mass starvation of thousands of nomads whose livestock and water points were destroyed by Barre's powers. A state is created by individuals who gave up their sovereignty and gave the state to execute on their behalf. In such a case, the state is allowed to make laws for the safety and control of land, and society accepts these laws for the public good. Statehood enables its inhabitants to harmonize their interests and create a just and equal society, but these aspirations have not existed in Somalia's military government. After the collapse of the military government in Somalia in 1991, the country went into more than two decades of civil war, terrorism, pirates, and clan wars. However, Somaliland took a different step towards peacebuilding, reconciliation, democratization, and state-building". It has avoided the devastation of warlordism that has afflicted the rest of Somalia through compromise politics between clan elders" (Adam, 1994).

The influence of clan leaders and the social structure rooted in clans took an essential role in Somaliland's state formation process. Somaliland is inhabited by three prominent clan families – the Isaq, Dir (mainly Gudabursi and Ise), and Harti Darod (Dhulbahante and Warsangeli), of which the Isaq is the majority of Somaliland's population (Musa & Horst, 2019). These clan families agreed on a cessation of hostilities and peaceful co-existence during a series of clan conferences, including Burao (1991), Sheikh (1992), Borama (1993), and Hargeisa (1996–1997) (Musa & Horst, 2019). The clan leaders' conferences paved the way for Somaliland's progress to an independent state. Burao conference is one of the most crucial in Somaliland's formation. Elders representing different clans from Somaliland unilaterally declared regaining independence from Somalia, annulling the Act of Union with Somalia from 1960. Any state has never recognized this unilateral declaration of independence. However, Somaliland has achieved "quasi-judicial" sovereignty where it has low-key

bilateral relations with a range of states and informal links with regional political organizations (Musa & Horst, 2019).

The democratization form compatible with SNM experience may be termed Consociational or power-sharing democracy (Steiner, 1991). Power-sharing facilitates reciprocal recognitions in societies fragmented by ethnic, clan, religious, and/or linguistic cleavages. Consociational democracy (industrial versions of which are practiced in Switzerland, Belgium, and Austria, for example) recognizes and acknowledges ethnic, clan, or religious cleavages in constituting cabinets and parliaments. Simultaneously, civil service and army recruitment are conducted based on both merit and proportionality – utilizing mechanisms similar to those of affirmative action procedures in the US. Attempts at forming governments based on grand coalitions are encouraged to reduce competition and potential conflicts. Each significant subgroup is allowed the right to veto legislation that is directly against an issue which it considers vital to its survival and well-being. Their particular group must endorse leaders to reflect the legitimacy needed to broker binding inter-group decisions and undertakings. In this connection, recent Oromo Liberation Front allegations that the new Ethiopian regime is creating ‘artificial leaders’ for the Oromos and other ethnic groups could, in the long run, jeopardize Ethiopia’s embryonic experiment with ‘ethnic democracy’. Since Ethiopia is so much larger in size and population than Eritrea and Somaliland, its initial attempts to establish consociationalism have appeared clumsy and confusing. Size also obliges Ethiopia to favor federalism and local autonomy to give consociationalism an implementation chance. On the other hand, the TPLF, with its vanguard party experience, may be tempted to imitate Eritrea with its class-oriented radical social democracy. Consociationalism is often strengthened by federal structures, decentralization, and local autonomy.

Consociational or power-sharing democracy can be called the democratization form consistent with SNM experience. "Consociational Democracy means government by elite cartel designed

to turn a democracy with a fragmented political culture into a stable democracy" (Lijphart, 1969, p. 216). In communities divided by cultural, clan, religious, and linguistic cleavages, power-sharing promotes mutual recognition. In establishing cabinets and parliaments, social democracy recognizes and recognizes racial, clan, or religious cleavages. At the same time, civil service and military recruitment are performed based on merit and proportionality, using US affirmative action procedures. Attempts to form governments based on grand coalitions are promoted to mitigate competition and future conflicts. Each important subgroup is given the power to legislate directly against a subject it considers essential to its life and well-being. Their particular community must accept leaders to represent the legitimacy needed to broker binding inter-group decisions and undertakings. Somaliland used this strategy to collect all clan leaders and create a coalition government in which each clan has a representative. Ethnic or clan-based power-sharing democracy is facilitated if the groups involved share a shared vision and common history (in this case, the history of British Somaliland as a separate entity, memories of inequities with the south and Siyad’s military oppression), the various groups occupy more or less defined areas and share similar perspectives on external threats (Adam, 1994). Thus, Somaliland employed the shared history to build the state where clan leaders played the most significant role without an international community’s support.

The elders of Somaliland came to establish a "Guurti" Council of Elders in Somali, which increased in significance as time passed. It constitutes one of the two legislative houses proposed for Somaliland in the constitution to be drawn up. The Guurti reached its height when it convened a Grand National Reconciliation Conference in Borama (a non-Isaq town) and helped elect Mohamed Ibrahim Egal, leader of the independence age president of the de facto Republic of Somaliland as the second president. The Borama Conference lasted from February until May of 1993 to make a whole series of binding compromises. The Guurti takes its

influence from the traditional Somali power-sharing composition and working.

Several assignments were carried out at the February-May Borama Meeting. As it considers peace and reconciliation as its primary mission, it has spent significant time adjudicating clan conflicts and disputes between neighbors. It addressed the essential provisions of an expected Constitution and proposed, for example, that the government structure be based on a model of the President/Vice-President rather than a model of the President/Prime Minister. They recommended the strict separation of the judiciary from the executive and legislative powers and bodies. They formally endorsed a National Assembly or Parliament consisting of two chambers, a Council of Elders and a lower famous Chamber of Representatives. On an interim basis, both of these latter exist together with a President (Isaaq), Vice-President (non-Isaaq from the Borama area), and a Cabinet selected according to the president's initiatives but sensitive to issues of merit and clan representativeness.

The Guurti is selected according to conventional procedure, historical precedent, and proportionality law. Somaliland is currently trying to avoid the pitfalls of direct, competitive multi-party elections, which during the 1960-69 era negatively politicized clanism and triggered instability and a military coup. The lower chamber elections consist of a series of mini-elections involving the classes and subgroups that are part of the experiment in Somaliland. These have contributed to a chamber dominated by new elites: retired politicians, businessmen, teachers and other civil servants, women's leaders, and other civil society organizations. At a recent regional meeting of the Elders' Council,

The Borama Conference was a significant event in Somaliland's history, as it led to the formation of an electoral body comprising 150 elders, politicians, SNM cadres, civil servants, and civil society leaders. This body conducted competitive elections, resulting in the election of veteran politician Ibrahim Mohamed Egal as the second President of Somaliland and Abdurahman Aw Ali, a veteran SNM leader, as

his Vice-President. The consociationalism system, a variant of liberal democracy, emphasizes the process rather than the product, and as such, disappointed SNM leaders were encouraged to accept the results and wait for the next elections in two years. A majority of the population, particularly the elders, had faith in Egal's leadership abilities and were willing to give him a second chance. It is noteworthy that the person who was tasked with consummating the union with ex-Italian Somalia is now responsible for guiding Somaliland out of the union.

Egal's government was successful in disarming the militias and integrating them into the national army. It also drafted Somaliland's national constitution, which established a multiparty and democratic system. The electoral system was transformed into a one-man, one-vote system. Egal's successor, Dahir Rayale Kahin, organized two presidential elections with multi-party competitions and parliamentary elections. In the 2010 presidential election, Ahmed Mohamed Mahamoud (Siilaanyo) emerged as the winner as an opposition leader. During his tenure, he implemented local government elections and the presidential election that brought the current president to power. Somaliland's statehood has progressed to the development stage, although it is still seeking recognition.

The Clannism Conundrum: Challenging the Path to Unified Statehood

Despite Somaliland's statehood's development, tribalism from different clans' interests is a relevant threat to Somaliland's statehood. Somaliland endured many outbreaks of clan-based civil war from 1991 to 1994, primarily caused by conflicts over economic facilities such as ports and airports. A significant cause of some of these disputes was the state's attempt to secure economic sources crucial for state-building. Successive governments sought to procure much-needed resources to execute state functions and establish state institutions. State-building is often a highly political operation, as Boege et al., (2008) remind us, which is likely to lead to confrontation as current distributions of

power are disputed. In the 1990s, similar struggles were fought in the state-formation phase in Somaliland. In 1992, for instance, the government tried to take over the Berbera seaport. The 1994 war similarly was triggered by president Egal's attempt to control Hargeisa Airport from the Edagalle clan. These and similar events, mostly involving Berbera port and Hargeisa airport, centered around different sub-clans within the Isaaq clan fighting for control over resources and claiming they were not well-represented politically (Adam, 1994).

Tribal Tensions: Navigating the Hurdles in Building Somaliland's State

In Somaliland's politics, tribalism plays the central role; even though a multi-party system is available, each part's key supporters are its clan affiliates. Thus, tribalism from different clans' interests in Somaliland is a relevant obstacle to Somaliland's statehood. Tribalism harms Somaliland's social, economic, political, and justice system. Somaliland endured many outbreaks of clan-based civil war from 1991 to 1994, primarily caused by conflicts over economic issues such as ports and airports. A significant cause of some of these disputes was the state's attempt to secure economic sources crucial for state-building. Successive governments sought to procure much-needed resources to execute state functions and establish state institutions. State-building is often a highly political operation, as Boege et al., (2008) remind us, which is likely to lead to confrontation as current distributions of power are disputed. In the 1990s, similar struggles were fought in the state-formation phase in Somaliland. In 1992, for instance, the government tried to take over the Berbera seaport. The 1994 war similarly was triggered by president Egal's attempt to control Hargeisa Airport from the Edagalle clan. These and similar events, mostly involving Berbera port and Hargeisa airport, centered around different sub-clans within the Isaaq clan fighting for control over resources and claiming they were not well-represented politically (Adam, 1994).

Tribal types and structures differ, but in Somaliland, communities are distinguished by cephalous tribal structures (headless). In traditional Somali society, clan affiliations were the cornerstone for survival, stability, and identity. Clan affiliations also help provide the normative structure that affects Somalis' attitudes and behaviors (Darod Ahmed, 2016). In their decisions concerning the creation of compensation arrangements for deaths and injuries, the society of Somaliland applies customary law. In particular, *xeer* (law) also defines land and water use agreements in this rural society. Elders are also the critical connection between rural communities and the district's authorities, regional and government, especially in conflicts and disasters. In this regard, tribalism still revives and functional in the government.

Clannism has impacts Somaliland's statehood in almost every aspect, mainly social, political, economic, and legal. Socially, for clan interests such as war preparedness, co-existence, economic cooperation, and genealogy issues, geographically, each tribe of Somali clans was concentrated and resided in a specific region. The organization and management of clan structures were fundamentally regulated primarily by clan elders such as sultans and akils. There were long historical wars between Somali tribes ecologically and geologically, focused on clan superiority/inferiority, water, pasture, and land disputes, along with intermittent and regular propaganda, biases, and stereotypes through poetry and traditional dances. These extreme biases undermined the social ties and interactions between the clans as they are located in separate areas for their genealogical settlements, and this adversely impacted social integrations, trust, co-existence, and cooperation that created a sensitive environment of conflict in which the most fragile and weak stability among the neighboring tribes.

In the political system of Somaliland, only individuals from particular clans can occupy key and prime positions in the government, and individuals pick and vote for candidates based on clannism. While it is structurally a democratic mechanism, all political officials, including the

president, ministries, legislative, and intelligence officers, are nominated by their clan dominance regardless of their credentials and backgrounds. Customary laws are influential over national laws in the sense of Somaliland. Somaliland aimed to create an environment where a democratic political system with multi parties competing with running the country. Elections, of any kind since 1969 in Somaliland, were vital due to the transition from a clan-oriented framework of power-sharing to a multi-party democracy-based parliamentary government to the post-war government system in Somaliland (Bradbury et al., 2003). Although many successful elections were held in Somaliland, clannism shapes the winner of the elections. In the political system of Somaliland, only individuals from particular clans can occupy key and prime positions in the government, and individuals pick and vote for candidates based on clannism. The political parties have no clear ideology that makes the people join or refuse them other than clannism.

According to Darod Ahmed (2016), the central government is strongly dominated by clan groups and leaders who use peaceful and less peaceful strategies to negotiate with the government. Clan rainbow systems were created by poor political representation and weak government structures, which challenged governments and created vulnerability to conflict and clan tensions. Also popular in the country are extravagant and mismanaged funds, skyrocketing corruption, lack of transparency, inequality, and low government structures and actions, leading to ongoing grievances and mistrust among clans.

Interestingly, Somaliland politicians' orient communities to step away from clannism while they are the primary beneficiaries of clannism. The politician's interest or concern on clannism depends on his/her situation. On the one hand, politicians use clannism for political gains to defend their party or administration. On the other hand, they criticize and oppose the administration when they do not see their interest. Clan-oriented political allies remain increasing in Somaliland; one of the most prominent is the so-called Jeegaan Allies. According to the former Minister of the

Presidency of Somaliland, Mahamoud Hashi, "Jeegaan Allies are individual clans uniting to gain their political interest and two allies will not build a nation" (Hadhwanaag TV, 2017).

Moreover, relatedly, Somaliland's current president publicly mentioned that the aftermath of the elections resulted in serious division among the population. The president said,

"My government's first two years have ended in bitterness and violence between clans over the election. We selected the democratic election system the election, but it is led to a problem for us. There was a pain, bulky of orphanages, and when we returned from civil war. When the elections took place, the losing family took it; they were beaten and fought. For a year and a half, we have been working to heal the wounds and restore the people's brotherhood. Thus, our successful clan, which I am their elder, prioritized everything to the other clan" (SAAB TV, 2020)".

The Somaliland president's speech shows how clannism shapes the politics in Somaliland. Thus, clannism is simultaneously in competition with statehood.

Forging Ahead: Conclusions and Pathways for Somaliland's Future

The article delves into the intricacies of clannism and statehood in Somaliland, emphasizing the crucial role of clan elders and the Guurti council in Somaliland's ceasefire, peacebuilding, and state-building efforts. Although the article acknowledges the indispensable role of traditional authority structures, it also recognizes the challenges posed by clannism to the aspirations of modern statehood.

By incorporating Weberian sociological concepts of authority, the article illustrates the dialectical relationship between traditional and legal-rational authority in Somaliland. This analysis reveals that the path to statehood in Somaliland is not only a political journey but also a sociological transition, navigating between deeply ingrained clan loyalties and the demands of a modern, legal-rational state system. Somaliland faces a daunting dilemma: either to

embrace a modern statehood model that fosters social unity, economic development, and international recognition or to remain entrenched in clan-oriented politics with its inherent risks of distrust, governance decline, and instability.

The paper suggests that the coexistence of clannism and statehood is fraught with challenges. Attempting to harmonize these fundamentally different forms of governance could have adverse consequences. However, the paper advocates for the potential of a nuanced approach, one that acknowledges the strengths of traditional authority while progressively integrating aspects of legal-rational governance. This approach demands a deep understanding of both traditional clan dynamics and the requirements of a modern state, guided by a methodological framework that combines sociological theory with practical political realities.

In conclusion, Somaliland's future statehood depends on a careful, informed balance between traditional clannism and the aspirations of a modern state. This balance is not only crucial for internal stability and development but also for achieving Somaliland's goal of international recognition. The path ahead for Somaliland is complex and multifaceted, necessitating a nuanced, theoretically informed, and pragmatic approach to nation-building.

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